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Dimeric Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) Complexes of Tridentate ONN Donor Ligands

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THE present communication deals with the preparation and characterization of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes with 2,5-dihydroxyacetophenone-*p*-iminoazobenzene (H_2L), 2,5-dihydroxypropionophenone-*p*-iminoazobenzene (H_2L') and 2,5-dihydroxybenzophenone-*p*-iminoazobenzene (H_2L'').

Experimental

2,5-Dihydroxyacetophenone/propionophenone/benzophenone¹ were refluxed with *p*-aminoazobenzene on a water-bath. The reaction mixture in each case was concentrated and cooled in a freezing bath. Shinning yellow Schiff bases that separated out by adding small pieces of ice to the reaction mixture were filtered and crystallised from alcohol. They are insoluble in water and soluble in common organic solvents. The melting points are 169, 182 and 155°, respectively.

Ethanolic solutions of the Schiff base and the metal salt ($CuCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ or $CoCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$) were mixed in 1:1 molar ratio and refluxed on a water-bath for 1.5 hr. The reaction mixture concentrated and the pH raised to 8 by adding 1:1 ammonia in alcohol, to give yellowish-green copper, bluish-green nickel and brownish-red cobalt complexes that were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in a desiccator.

Nitrogen, chloride and metal ions were estimated by the standard methods². Molar conductance of the complexes was measured in DMF and the molecular weight was determined cryoscopically³. The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a Gouy balance. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The analytical, conductance, magnetic and spectral data of the complexes are recorded in Table 1. The elemental analyses indicate 1:1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry. The low molar conductance values of the complexes are ascribed to their non-electrolytic nature. The observed molecular weight values of the complexes suggest their dimeric character.

The assignments of ir bands of the ligands and the complexes are based on literature^{4,5}. In the ligands, the band observed at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to νOH frequency and the additional band broad and weak at $\sim 2800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to νOH involved in intramolecular H-bonding with basic azomethine nitrogen. In the complexes the νOH band is retained whereas the low frequency band disappears suggesting that the phenolic proton involved in O-H...N bonding is lost on complex formation. This is further confirmed by the appearance of a new $\nu(M-O)$ band at $\sim 480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. However, the $\nu(C-H)$ band observed at $\sim 3070\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands is not affected on complex formation. The strong band due to $\nu(C=N)$ observed at $\sim 1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligands is found to shift by 15-20 cm^{-1} to lower frequency region on complex formation. This suggests that the azomethine nitrogen is bonded to the metal ion. The $\nu(M-N)$ band is observed in the complexes at $\sim 385\text{ cm}^{-1}$. It is cumbersome to assign the $\nu(N=N)$ mode to a specific band due to extensive coupling amongst $\nu(C=C)$, $\nu(C=N)$ and $\nu(N=N)$ modes. However, the band observed at $\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is tentatively assigned to coupled $\nu(C=C)$ and $\nu(N=N)$ modes. This band shifts by 45-65 cm^{-1} to lower frequency region in the complexes suggesting that the nitrogen of N=N group is bonded to metal ion. The occurrence of $\nu(M-Cl)$ band at $\sim 340\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes indicate that the chlorine atom occupies the fourth coordination position of the metal(II) ions.

The μ_{eff} values of the complexes (Table 1) are slightly less than the values suggested for a tetrahedral geometry⁶. The ligand geometry (Fig. 1) indicates that a monomeric structure involves much steric hindrance. A dimeric formulation requires appreciable reduction in the magnetic moment values of a complex. In the case of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes the magnetic moment values are close to their spin-only values. We suggest a

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NOTES

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC AND SPECTRAL DATA OF M(HL)Cl

Complexes	Found/(Calcd.)			Λ_M mhos cm^2 mole $^{-1}$	μ_{eff} (B.M.)	λ_{max} (ϵ_{max}) (nm)	IR-spectral (cm^{-1}) Complex/(Ligand)		
	Mol wt	%Metal	%N				$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$	$\nu(\text{N}=\text{N})+\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$	
Cu(HL)Cl	850 (429)	14.68 (14.81)	9.63 (9.79)	8.36 (8.28)	3.5	1.71	390(4685) 760(120)	1615 (1630)	1525 (1590)
Cu(HL')Cl	795 (443)	14.42 (14.34)	9.59 (9.47)	8.12 (8.01)	2.8	1.73	380(4650) 770(145)	1615 (1635)	1530 (1580)
Cu(HL'')Cl	940 (491)	12.81 (12.94)	8.42 (8.54)	7.33 (7.23)	3.3	1.68	390(4770) 770(150)	1610 (1635)	1525 (1570)
Ni(HL)Cl	820 (424)	13.98 (13.89)	9.82 (9.90)	8.26 (8.37)	5.5	2.92	390(4970), 580(395), 870(102)	1610 (1630)	1530 (1590)
Ni(HL')Cl	810 (438)	13.38 (13.45)	9.68 (9.59)	8.18 (8.17)	6.2	2.83	390(4915), 580(355), 880(103)	1615 (1635)	1530: (1580)
Ni(HL'')Cl	920 (486)	12.25 (12.12)	8.52 (8.64)	7.42 (7.30)	4.3	2.98	380(4860), 590(345), 880(115)	1620 (1635)	1525 (1570)
Co(HL)Cl	790 (424)	13.75 (13.89)	9.81 (9.89)	8.45 (8.36)	4.2	3.63	390(5280), 580(425), 820(110)	1610 (1630)	1535 (1590)
Co(HL')Cl	830 (438)	13.58 (13.44)	9.45 (9.58)	8.13 (8.09)	5.3	3.68	380(5150), 590(525), 820(98)	1620 (1635)	1530 (1580)
Co(HL'')Cl	895 (486)	12.22 (12.11)	8.74 (8.63)	7.18 (7.29)	4.6	3.52	380(5290), 590(490), 830(95)	1615 (1635)	1525 (1570)

R = CH₃, C₂H₅ and C₆H₅⁻

Fig. 1

dimeric structure with tetrahedral geometry for these complexes and their observed magnetic behaviour is attributed to a less prominent antiferromagnetic spin-exchange between metal(II) ions in the dimer^{7,8} (Fig. 2). Similar magnetic behaviour of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes with

(II)

M = Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II)

Fig. 2

antiferromagnetic spin-exchange has also been observed earlier^{9,10}. The tetrahedral configuration for Cu(II) complexes is forced due to steric properties and interligand repulsion^{11,12}.

The complexes and the ligand exhibit a strong electronic spectral band at ~ 390 nm due to the ligand $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition¹³. Cu(II) complexes show a ligand field band at ~ 760 nm assignable to $^3T_2 \rightarrow ^3E$ transition¹⁴. Two weak ligand field bands observed at ~ 870 and ~ 580 nm in the spectra of Ni(II) complexes are attributed to $^3T_1 \rightarrow ^3A_2$ (F)

and $^3T_1 \rightarrow ^3T_1$ (P) transitions, respectively¹⁴. Co(II) complexes also exhibit two weak ligand field bands at ~ 820 and ~ 590 nm assigned to $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^4T_1$ (F) and $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^4T_1$ (P) transitions, respectively¹⁴.

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